

FRACTIONAL WORTH OF AN ASSET PRICING MODEL USING A SKEW RANDOM PRICING TREE

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Abstract: Motivated by existing models in literature, this work aims at developing a tree pricing model with underlying asset price dynamics following Itô-Mckean skew fractional Brownian motion (FBM). The intention is to reduce the Black-Scholes option pricing equation modeled by fractional Brownian motion to a one dimensional heat equation and then obtain the solution by applying the Laplace transform method (LTM). A sensitivity analysis for worth profile is carried out with some examples in a concrete setting, have knowledge of the binomial method of option pricing as well as the tree theory.

Keywords: Worth Profile; FBM; Binomial Tree; Option pricing.

INTRODUCTION

In the academic literature on dynamic asset pricing theory, discrete-time option pricing models, traditionally play a subordinated role to their continuous-time counterparts ([Bock & Korn, 2016; Shirvani et al., 2020) ^[1, 2]. This is due to the highly developed theory of semi martingales, Lévy processes and the fundamental theorem of asset pricing (Jarrow, 2012; Protter, 2004; Guasoni et al., 2012) ^[3, 4, 5]. An option is one of the widely and most commonly used financial products in the market that allows you to trade the price of the market in the future, bond futures, currency futures, commodity equities, and interest rate futures (Li, 2019) ^[6]. The Black – Scholes Model is commonly used for option pricing, which is one of the most important applications in finance. In the absence of a transaction cost, the value of the option is determined by using B-S model. In the view of Caputo sense Vijayan & Manimaran, 2023) ^[7], proposes a result for the fractional Black–Scholes equation (FBSE) problem. Their main goal was to show how to solve the FBSE by a semi-analytical method called the homotopy analysis shehu transform method (HASTM) and compare that homotopy analysis method (HAM), homotopy perturbation method (HPM), elzaki transform homotopy perturbation method (ETHPM). Fractional calculus has become of increasing use for analyzing not only stochastic processes driven by fractional Brownian processes (Osu & Chukwunezu, 2016) ^[8]. Fractional Brownian motion of Hurst exponent $H \in (0, 1)$ is a stochastic process $\{B_H(t), t \in \mathbb{R}\}$ which satisfies the following :

1. $B_H(t)$ is Gaussian, that is, for every $t > 0$, $B_H(t)$ has a normal distribution

2. $B_H(t)$ is a self similar process meaning that for any $\alpha > 0$, $B_H(\alpha, t)$ has the same law as $\alpha^H B_H(t)$.

3. It has stationary increments, that is, $B_H(t) - B_H(s) \sim B_H(t - s)$.

Mandlbrov (1963)^[9] studied the Fractional Brownian motion (FBM) and discovered many of its properties.

Fractional Brownian motion can be applied in pricing financial derivatives. A financial derivative is an instrument whose price depends on, or is derived from the value of another asset. Often, this underlying asset is a stock. The concept of financial derivative is not new. While there remains some historical debate as to the exact date of the creation of financial derivatives, it is well accepted that the first attempt at modern derivative pricing began with the work of Charles Castelly (Hui, 2012)^[10]. The Black-Scholes option pricing equation modeled by fractional Brownian motion is derived by replacing the standard Brownian motion involved in the classical Black-Scholes with fractional Brownian motion which contains the Hurst exponent, H . The Hurst exponent denoted by H , is a statistical measure used to classify time series. The value of H varies between 0 and 1. The binomial formula given by Cox et al (1979)^[11] is a tool for evaluating the call option price. It is well known that the price from the binomial formula converges to the price from the Black-Scholes formula, which was given, by Black & Scholes (1973)^[12] as the number of periods (n) converges to infinity. Osu & Duruojinkeya (2023)^[13], however proposed a formula for the worth of the expected returns of options and stock according to risk characteristics. Here the knowledge of the binomial method of option pricing as well as the tree was applied in calculating the fair value of options. At each node of the tree, two possible outcomes were considered: an increase in the price of the underlying asset and a decrease in the price of the underlying asset.

Motivated by this model, we aim at developing a tree pricing model with underlying asset price dynamics following Itô-Mckean skew fractional Brownian motion. In order to obtain the formula for the worth profile at each node of the tree, we reduce the Black-Scholes option pricing equation modeled by fractional Brownian motion to a one dimensional heat equation and then obtain the solution by applying the Laplace transform Method.

Tree theory is applied in many areas of mathematics and it forms an interesting part of combinational set theory.

Definition 1.1: Mathematically a tree is a partially ordered set $T = \langle T_1 \leq T \rangle$ such that for every $X \in T$, the set $x = \{y \in T: y <_T x\}$ is well-ordered by $\leq T$.

It is customary to represent trees n pictures from as illustrated below;

1(a)

1(b)

Fig.1: General Tree

Figure 1 shows trees with n -vertices with $(n - 1)$ edges. The watering in figure 1(a) depicts the government policies which may lead to a garden in figure 1(b) when the policies are favorable for investment. This leads to the worth profiles of investors becoming like trees planted by the rivers of waters (Psalms 1 verse 3).

The tree works by using the formula for a single period call option; it can be expanded to a two-period call option up to n -period call option. Then n -period look-alike options using the binomial tree pricing formula is; divide the option effective period T into a small interval as Δt and at each Δt the stock price changes from S to S_u or S_d . In this case, if the possibility of an upward price movement is P then the possibility of the downward movement is $1 - P$. We find the formula by using a risk-neutral pricing principle because the rate of change in the underlying asset follows a normal distribution. The binomial tree option pricing model has already established itself as one of the primary pricing standards for major stock exchanges worldwide (Osu & Duruojinkeya, 2023) [13].

The problem is to find the worth of a stock at each point of the tree of Fig.1.

Observe from Fig.1 that each point satisfies a polar form of a diffusion equation in a spherical coordinate system written as (Datta & Pal, 2018) [14]:

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} = \frac{k}{s^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(s^2 \frac{\partial V}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{s^2 \sin \theta} \frac{\partial V}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{\partial V}{\partial \theta} \right) + \frac{1}{s^2 \sin^2 \theta} \frac{d^2 V}{d\phi^2}. \quad (1)$$

Where; w = the worth of the stock, k = diffusion coefficient, (S, θ, ϕ) = point in spherical coordinate and S is the stock price.

In the radial direction, one-dimension form of (1) can be written as:

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2} + r(t)S \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} - r(t)V = 0, \quad (2)$$

with $w(0, t) = 0$, $w(S, t) \sim S$ as $S \rightarrow \infty$, where $V =, V(S, t) =$ European option prices; $S =$ Asset price, $t =$ Time, $r =$ Risk-free rate, $\sigma =$ Volatility.

Definition 1 The Riemann-Liouville fractional integral of f with order μ is defined by

$$\mathbb{I}^\mu f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\mu)} \int_0^x (x - \tau)^{\mu-1} f(\tau) d\tau \quad (3)$$

Definition 2 The Riemann-Liouville fractional derivative of f with order μ is defined by

$$D_x^\mu f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(m-\mu)} \frac{d^m}{dx^m} \int_0^x (x-\tau)^{m-\mu-1} f(\tau) d\tau \quad (4)$$

$${}_k^C D_x^\mu f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(m-\mu)} \frac{d^m}{dx^m} \int_0^x (x\tau)^{m-\mu-1} f(\tau) d\tau \quad (5)$$

Definition 4 The Mittag-Leffler is defined as

$$E_\alpha = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{\Gamma(\alpha k + 1)}, \alpha > 0, z \in \mathbb{C}, k = 0, 1, \dots \quad (6)$$

2. FRACTIONAL OPTION PRICING MODEL

Based on replicating portfolio that ensures that no arbitrage opportunities are allowed, a fractional B-S option can be derived. In what follows, we state:

Proposition 2.1: *Let a generic payoff function $G(t) = V(S, t)$. Then the partial differential equation associated with the price of the derivative on the stock price is*

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial t} + H\sigma^2 S^2 t^{2H-1} \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial S^2} + rS \frac{\partial v}{\partial S} - rv = 0, \quad S > 0, t > 0, \quad (7)$$

$$H \in (0, 1), H \neq \frac{1}{2}.$$

Where v is the call option price, t is the time to maturity, H is the Hurst exponent, σ is the volatility, S is the stock price and r is the discount rate.

Proof: The stock price S follows the fractional Brownian motion process

$$dS = \mu S dt + \sigma S dB_H(t). \quad (8)$$

The wealth of an investor X_t follows a diffusion process given by

$$dX = \Lambda dS + r(X - \Lambda S) dt. \quad (9)$$

Putting equation (8) into equation (9) yields

$$dX = \{rX + \Lambda S(\mu - r)\} dt + \Lambda S \sigma dB_H(t). \quad (10)$$

Where $\mu - r$ is the risk premium. Suppose that the value of this claim at time t is given by

$$G(t) = v(S, t), S = S_t. \quad (11)$$

Applying the Ito's formula for fractional Brownian motion on equation (11), we have

$$dG = \frac{\partial v}{\partial t} dt + \frac{\partial v}{\partial S} dS + Ht^{2H-1} \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial S^2} (dS)^2. \quad (12)$$

Substituting (8) in (12), we have

$$dG = \frac{\partial v}{\partial t} dt + \frac{\partial v}{\partial S} [\mu S dt + \sigma S dB_H(t)] + Ht^{2H-1} \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial S^2} [\mu S dt + \sigma S dB_H(t)]^2. \quad (13)$$

$$\Rightarrow dG = \frac{\partial v}{\partial t} dt + \frac{\partial v}{\partial S} [\mu S dt + \sigma S dB_H(t)] +$$

$$Ht^{2H-1} \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial S^2} [\mu^2 S^2 (dt)^2 + 2\mu\sigma S^2 dt dB_H(t) + \sigma^2 S^2 (dB_H(t))^2]. \quad (14)$$

Multiplication rule implies:

$$(dt)^2 = 0; (dB_H(t))^2 = dt$$

Thus (14) reduces to

$$dG = \frac{\partial v}{\partial t} dt + \frac{\partial v}{\partial S} [\mu S dt + \sigma S dB_H(t)] + Ht^{2H-1} \sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial S^2} dt. \quad (15)$$

Collecting like terms we have

$$dG = \left[\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \mu S \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} + H t^{2H-1} \sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2} \right] dt + \sigma S \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} dB_H(t) \quad (16)$$

Using (11) we have;

$$dV = \left[\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \mu S \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} + H t^{2H-1} \sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2} \right] dt + \sigma S \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} dB_H(t). \quad (17)$$

Thus, equating coefficients, we have

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \mu S \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} H \sigma^2 S^2 t^{2H-1} \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2} = rV + \Lambda_t S (\mu - r) \quad (18)$$

and

$$\sigma S \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} = \Lambda_t \sigma S \quad (19)$$

or

$$\Lambda_t = \frac{\partial V}{\partial S}. \quad (20)$$

Substituting equation (20) into (18), we have

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \mu S \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} H \sigma^2 S^2 t^{2H-1} \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2} = rV + S \mu \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} - S r \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} \quad (21)$$

This implies equation (2) as required.

3. *The Solution of Equation (2) using Laplace transform method*

To obtain the formula for the worth profile at each node of the tree, we first reduce the Black-Scholes option pricing equation modeled by fractional Brownian motion to a one dimensional heat equation and then obtain the solution by applying the Laplace transform Method. In the sequel, we state;

Proposition 3.1: *Let equation (7) be given by*

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + H t^{2H-1} S^2 \sigma^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2} + r S \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} - rV = 0, \quad S > 0, t > 0; V(0, t) = 0, V(S, t) \sim S \quad \text{as} \\ S \rightarrow \infty, V(S, t) = \max\{|S - K|, 0\} \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Then (22) can be reduced to one-dimensional heat equation of the form

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial \tau} = p \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2}. \quad (23)$$

Proof: Set

$$\tau = \frac{\sigma^2(T-t)}{2}, x = \ln(S/K) \quad (24)$$

and

$$V(S, t) = K v(x, \tau). \quad (25)$$

Differentiating (24) and (25), we have

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} = K \frac{\partial V}{\partial \tau} \cdot \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial t} = \left(K \frac{\partial V}{\partial \tau} \right) \left(-\frac{\sigma^2}{2} \right), \quad (26)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} &= K \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{\partial x}{\partial S} = K \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \left(\frac{1}{S}\right) = \frac{K}{S} \frac{\partial v}{\partial x}, \quad (27) \\ \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial S} \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial S}\right) = \frac{\partial}{\partial S} \left(\frac{K}{S} \frac{\partial v}{\partial x}\right) = \frac{K}{S} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial S} \frac{\partial v}{\partial x}\right) + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial S} \frac{K}{S}\right) \\ &= \frac{K}{S} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial S} \frac{\partial v}{\partial x}\right) + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \left(\frac{-K}{S^2}\right) = \frac{K}{S} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial x}\right) \frac{dx}{dS}\right] - \frac{K}{S^2} \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} = \frac{K}{S} \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} \left(\frac{1}{S}\right) - \frac{K}{S^2} \frac{\partial v}{\partial x}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2} = -\frac{K}{S^2} \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + \frac{K}{S^2} \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2}. \quad (28)$$

The terminal condition is

$$V(S, T) = \max\{|S - K|, 0\} = \max\{|Ke^x - K|, 0\}.$$

Let

$$\begin{aligned} V(S, T) &= Kv(x, 0) \\ \Rightarrow v(x, 0) &= \max\{|e^x - 1|, 0\} \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

Substitute (26), (27) and (28) in (22) and get

$$\left(K \frac{\partial v}{\partial \tau}\right) \left(\frac{\sigma^2}{2}\right) + H \left(T - \frac{2\tau}{\sigma^2}\right)^{2H-1} S^2 \sigma^2 \left(-\frac{K}{S^2} \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + \frac{K}{S^2} \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2}\right) + rS \left(\frac{K}{S} \frac{\partial v}{\partial x}\right) - rKv = 0. \quad (30)$$

Let (the correlation coefficient)

$$m = \frac{2\tau}{\sigma^2}, \quad (31)$$

then we have

$$-\frac{\sigma^2}{2} \frac{\partial v}{\partial \tau} + H(T - m)^{2H-1} S^2 \sigma^2 \left(-\frac{1}{S^2} \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{S^2} \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2}\right) + rS \left(\frac{1}{S} \frac{\partial v}{\partial x}\right) - rv = 0, \quad (32)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} &-\frac{\sigma^2}{2} \frac{\partial v}{\partial \tau} + H(T - m)^{2H-1} \sigma^2 \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + H(T - m)^{2H-1} \sigma^2 \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + r \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - rv \\ &= -\frac{\sigma^2}{2} \frac{\partial v}{\partial \tau} + H(T - m)^{2H-1} \sigma^2 \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - r \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - H(T - m)^{2H-1} \sigma^2 \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + rv \\ &= \frac{\sigma^2}{2} \frac{\partial v}{\partial \tau} + [H(T - m)^{2H-1} \sigma^2 - r] \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - H(T - m)^{2H-1} \sigma^2 \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + rv \\ &= \frac{\partial v}{\partial \tau} + \left[2H(T - m)^{2H-1} - \frac{2r}{\sigma^2}\right] \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - 2H(T - m)^{2H-1} \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + \frac{2rv}{\sigma^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

Let

$$p = 2H(T - m)^{2H-1} \quad (34)$$

Then one has

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial \tau} + (p - q) \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - p \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + qv = 0 \quad (35)$$

or

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial \tau} = p \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + (q - p) \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - qv. \quad (36)$$

Furthermore let

$$v(x, \tau) = e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} u(x, \tau). \quad (37)$$

Then using the product rule, we have

$$\begin{aligned} v_\tau &= \beta e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} u + e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} u_\tau, \\ v_x &= \alpha e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} u + e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} u_x \end{aligned}$$

and

$$v_{xx} = \alpha^2 e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} u + 2\alpha e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} u_x + e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} u_{xx}.$$

Where v_τ and v_x stand for the first partial derivative of v with respect to τ and x respectively. u_τ and u_x stand for the first partial derivative of u with respect to τ and x respectively. v_{xx} and u_{xx} stand for the second partial derivative of v and u with respect to x .

Substituting into (37), one gets

$$\begin{aligned} & \beta e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} u + e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} u_\tau \\ \Rightarrow & p[\alpha^2 e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} u + 2\alpha e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} u_x + e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} u_{xx}] + (q - p)[\alpha e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} u + e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} u_x] - q e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} u. \end{aligned}$$

Simplifying one has $\beta u + u_\tau = p[\alpha^2 u + 2\alpha u_x + u_{xx}] + (q - p)(\alpha u + u_x) - qu$,
 $u_\tau = pu_{xx} + [2\alpha p + (q - p)]u_x + [\alpha^2 p + (q - p)\alpha - q - \beta]u.$ (38)

Choose

$$\alpha = \frac{p-q}{2p} \text{ and } \beta = \frac{-(p+q)^2}{4p}. \quad (39)$$

Thus (38) is reduced to

$$u_\tau = pu_{xx}. \quad (40)$$

Equation (40) is a one dimensional heat equation. One can solve (40) using Laplace transform method.

Theorem 3.1: Let the worth profile $u(x, t)$ in each nod (as in figure 1) obey the heat diffusion equation of equation (40).

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} u(x, t) = p \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} u(x, t), \quad (41)$$

such that initial worth distribution $u(x) = u_0$. At $t = 0$, the worth at the half end is changed instantaneously to $u(0, t) = 0$ and kept at the worth profile for all $t > 0$, Then

- (i) $v(x, \tau) = e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} \frac{x}{2\sqrt{\pi 2H(T-m)^{2H-1} t^3}} \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{x^2}{4p 2H(T-m)^{2H-1} t} + t\right)\right\}$, if one assumes a solution for < 0 , and
- (ii). $v(x, \tau) = u_0 e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} \operatorname{erfc}\left(\frac{x}{2\sqrt{2H(T-m)^{2H-1} t}}\right)$ if > 0 .

Proof:

The Laplace of the left-hand side of (41) gives;

$$L\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} u(x, t)\right) = s\phi(x, s) - u(x, 0) = s\phi(x, s) - u_0. \quad (42)$$

And of the right-hand side:

$$L\left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} u(x, t)\right) = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \phi(x, s),$$

which gives

$$s\phi(x, s) - T_0 = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \phi(x, s) \rightarrow \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \phi(x, s) - s\phi(x, s) = u_0$$

or

$$\frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x^2} - \frac{s}{p} \phi = u_0. \quad (43)$$

Consider

$$\phi'' - \frac{s}{p} \phi = u_0. \quad (44)$$

Then this has the particular integral

$$\phi'' - \frac{s}{p} \phi = 0,$$

with auxiliary equation

$$n^2 - \frac{s}{p} = 0,$$

with

$$n = \pm \sqrt{\frac{s}{p}}.$$

And from here this is solved by considering cases for $s = 0, s > 0$. For $s < 0$, *misimaginary* and the solution for

$$\phi = c_1 \cos\left(\sqrt{\frac{s}{p}}x\right) + c_2 \sin\left(\sqrt{\frac{s}{p}}x\right) = e^{\sqrt{\frac{s}{p}}x}, c_1 = c_2 = 1. \quad (45)$$

There should not be a need to consider $s < 0$, as the Laplace variable is usually assumed to be > 0 by definition and one has not considered any separation of variables. However, if one considers equation (45) as a solution then the inverse transform will give

$$u(x, t) = \frac{x}{2\sqrt{\pi p t^3}} \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{x^2}{4pt} + t\right)\right\}. \quad (46)$$

Combining (46) and (37) gives the worth profile in this case as (using (34));

$$v(x, \tau) = e^{\alpha x + \beta} \frac{x}{2\sqrt{\pi 2H(T-m)^{2H-1} t^3}} \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{x^2}{4p 2H(T-m)^{2H-1} t} + t\right)\right\} \quad (47)$$

Now set

$$\begin{aligned} L_t(n(x, t)) &= U(x, s), \\ L(u'') &= L(\dot{u}) \rightarrow U''(x, s) = \frac{s}{4} U(s, s) - \frac{1}{4} u(x, 0). \end{aligned}$$

Then (with a sign error), one gets;

$$\phi_{xx} - \frac{s}{p} \phi = -u_0. \quad (48)$$

For each fixed s , this is a constant-coefficient second-order linear ODE in x . The general solution is given by the sum of the general solution to the homogenous equation. So for $s > 0$ the solution is given as a sum of $c_1 e^{\sqrt{\frac{s}{p}}x} + c_2 e^{-\sqrt{\frac{s}{p}}x}$ and by impection $\phi_p(x) = \frac{u_0}{s/p}$ is a solution of the inhomogeneous equation.

Using the initial-value theorem for the Laplace transform ($f(0) = \lim_{s \rightarrow \infty} sF(s)$) to show that $c_1 = 0$. The boundary condition $\phi(0, t) = 0$ implies $\phi(0, s) = 0$ for all $s > 0$, which then implies $c_2 = -\frac{u_0}{s/p}$. Altogether from here we obtain the Laplace transform is

$$\phi(x, s) = -u_0 \frac{e^{-\sqrt{\frac{s}{p}}x}}{s/p} + \frac{u_0}{s/p}. \quad (49)$$

We then invert this Laplace transform. The second term just gives a unit step function and while the inverse Laplace transform of the first term cannot be expressed in terms of elementary functions, we can express it using the rule

$$\frac{F(s)}{s} = L \left[\int_0^t f(\tau) d\tau \right] (s), \quad (50)$$

which gives

$$\phi(x, t) = -T_0 \int_0^t L^{-1} \left[e^{-\sqrt{\frac{s}{p}}x} \right] (\tau) d\tau + u_0 u(t). \quad (51)$$

Where $u(t)$ is the unit step function. The inverse Laplace transform in the integral gives

$$u(x, t) = L^{-1} \left[e^{-\sqrt{\frac{s}{p}}x} \right] (\tau) = \frac{x e^{-\frac{x^2}{4\tau}}}{2\sqrt{p\pi\tau^3}}, \quad (52)$$

Making the change of variable $\eta = \frac{x}{2\sqrt{\tau}}$ or equivalently $\tau = \frac{x^2}{4\eta^2}$, $d\tau = \frac{x^2}{2\eta^3} d\eta$ gives

$$\int_0^{-1} L^{-1} \left[e^{-\sqrt{\frac{s}{p}}xx} \right] (\tau) d\tau = \frac{2}{\sqrt{p\pi}} \int_{\frac{x}{2\sqrt{t}}}^{\infty} e^{-\eta^2} d\eta = \operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{x}{2\sqrt{pt}} \right). \quad (53)$$

Where erfc denotes the complementary error function. Therefore, the solution comes out to

$$u(x, t) = u_0 \operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{x}{2\sqrt{pt}} \right) - u_0 u(t). \quad (54)$$

To check that this is consistent with the initial and boundary conditions at $t = 0$,

$\operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{pt}} \right) = 0$ for all $x > 0$, so $\phi(x, 0) = u_0$ for all $x > 0$,

While at $x = 0$, one can explicitly calculate the value of $\operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{s}{p} \right)$ (It is half of the famous Gaussian

Integral) to find that $u(0, t) = -u_0 + u_0 = 0$.

Therefore

$$u(x, t) = u_0 \operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{x}{2\sqrt{pt}} \right) \text{ as } u(t) \uparrow 0. \quad (55)$$

Combining (55) and (37) gives the worth profile in this case as (using (34))

$$;v(x, \tau) = u_0 e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} \operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{x}{2\sqrt{2H(T-m)^{2H-1}\tau}} \right). \quad (56)$$

4 Sensitivity Analysis for the Skewed Profile and Some numerical examples

A levy process $(v(\tau))_{\tau \geq 0}$ with a nonnegative increment is called a subordinator. The Laplace transform of $v(\tau)$ has the form $\mathbb{E}[e^{-\alpha v(\tau)}] = e^{-r\varphi(v)}$, ≥ 0 with the Laplace exponent $\varphi(v)$ given by

$$\varphi(z) = \beta z + \int_0^{\infty} (1 - e^{-xz}) d\rho(x).$$

For any complex z with the $Re z \geq 0$, where $\beta \geq 0$ is a drift parameter and ρ is a measure satisfying $\int_0^{\infty} \min\{1, x\} d\rho(x) < +\infty$ which is called Levy measure of $(v(\tau))_{\tau \geq 0}$.

For $\alpha \in (0,1)$, the Levy measure of $v_\alpha(t)$ is absolutely continuous with respect to the Lebesgue measure on $(0, +\infty)$ with the density function (as in the set of equations (3-6);

$$h_\alpha(x) = \frac{\alpha}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} x^{-\alpha-1}, x > 0. \quad (57)$$

It therefore suggests that $[v_\rho(t)]_{t \geq 0}$ is a stochastic process with Laplace transform;

$$\mathbb{E} e^{-\mu v_\rho(\tau)} = e^{-\tau \varphi_\rho(\mu)}, \quad (58)$$

with a subordinator, where $\varphi_\rho(u) \geq \int_0^\tau v^x d\gamma(x)$ and γ is a Borel probability measure on $(0,1)$.

Park & Nguyen (2023)^[15] studied the Black-Litterman (BL) asset allocation model under the hidden truncation skew-normal distribution. When returns are assumed to follow this skew normal distribution, they showed that the posterior returns, after incorporating views, are also skew normal.

Let $v = \{v_t, t \geq 0\}$ be a standard Brownian Motion generating a stochastic basis $[(\Omega, \mathbb{F} = (\mathfrak{F}_t = \sigma(v_\alpha, \alpha \leq t): t \geq 0, P)(Li, 2019)^{[6]}$.

Let $\alpha \in (0,1)$ and set

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}_t^{(\alpha)} &= \int_0^\tau \alpha^2 I_{\{v_s \geq 0\}} + (1 - \alpha)^2 I_{\{v_s < 0\}} ds, \\ \tau_t^{(\alpha)} &= \inf\{s \geq 0: \mathcal{A}_s^{(\alpha)} > t\}, t \geq 0, \\ v_t^{(\alpha)} &= \varphi_\alpha(v_{\tau_t^{(\alpha)}}), t > 0, v_0^{(\alpha)} > 0. \end{aligned}$$

Where $\varphi_\alpha(x) = \alpha x I_{\{x \geq 0\}} + (1 - \alpha)x I_{\{x < 0\}}, x \in R$. Then the process $v^{(\alpha)} = \{v_t^{(\alpha)}, t \geq 0\}$ is called a skewed Brownian Motion (SBM) with parameter α . For every $t \geq 0$, the density $f_t^\alpha(x), x \in R$ of $v_t^\alpha(x)$ is given by;

$$v_t^\alpha(x) = \begin{cases} \alpha \left[u_0 e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} \operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{x}{2\sqrt{2H(T-m)^{2H-1}t}} \right) \right], & \text{if } x \geq 0 \\ (1 - \alpha) \left[e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} \frac{x}{2\sqrt{\pi 2H(T-m)^{2H-1}t^3}} \exp \left\{ - \left(\frac{x^2}{4p 2H(T-m)^{2H-1}t} + t \right) \right\}, \right] & \text{if } x < 0 \end{cases} \quad (59)$$

In order to find the worth of a stock at each point of tree, equation (59) can be written in polar coordinate system as;

$$v_t^\alpha(\rho) = \begin{cases} \alpha \left[u_0 e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} \operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{\rho \cos \theta}{2\sqrt{2H(T-m)^{2H-1}t}} \right) \right], & \text{if } \rho \geq 0 \\ (1 - \alpha) \left[e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} \frac{\rho \cos \theta}{2\sqrt{\pi 2H(T-m)^{2H-1}t^3}} \exp \left\{ - \left(\frac{(\rho \cos \theta)^2}{4p 2H(T-m)^{2H-1}t} + t \right) \right\}, \right] & \text{if } \rho < 0 \end{cases} \quad (60)$$

where $x = \rho \cos \theta$.

Equation (60) is the worth profile at each node with the possibilities of up or down nodes of the tree as in figure 1b.

Now assume an expected volume of portfolio at each node of a tree (see figure 1) given values τ, m, p, q, α and β as calculated from equations (24), (31),(34) and (39) respectively. Then the worth distribution in the volume of portfolio at time, t , at each node is as in figures 2 and 3 below probability up or down

Figure 2: Worth profiles of equation (47), for the down nodes of the tree of equation (59). Substituting different Values of the Parameters $p, q, t, \alpha, \beta, r$ for the 3D Graphs, we calculate the expected value $v(x, t)$ with current price of a stock $\rho_0 = \$120$ and the expiry date is 363day, the size of the up move $\alpha = 0.131$ and the risk free rate $r = 0.09$. We use a binomial tree, to determine the current worth of the option. Herein, we determine the probability for stock price upturn uniquely as $P_\alpha = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{|\alpha - \beta^2/2|}{\beta} \sqrt{\Delta t}$, $P_\alpha = 0.521, P_\beta = 0.479, \beta = 0.242$, where $P_\alpha, P_\beta = 1 - P_\alpha$ are the probabilities of up or down nodes of the tree as in figure 1b and $\Delta t = 0.05$.

Figure 3: Worth profiles of equation (56), for up node of the tree of equation (60). Substituting different Values of the Parameters $p, q, t, \alpha, \beta, r$ for the 3D Graphs, we calculate the expected value $v(x, t)$ with current price of a stock $\rho_0 = \$120$ and the expiry date is 363day, the size of the up move $\alpha = 0.131$ and the risk free rate $r = 0.09$. We use a binomial tree, to determine the current worth of the option. Herein, we determine the probability for stock price upturn uniquely as $P_\alpha =$

$\frac{1}{2} + \frac{|\alpha - \beta^2/2|}{\beta} \sqrt{\Delta t} P_\alpha = 0.521, P_\beta = 0.479, \beta = 0.242,$ where $P_\alpha, P_\beta = 1 - P_\alpha$ are the probabilities of up or down nodes of the tree as in figure 1b and $\Delta t = 0.05$.

Figures 4(a,b) below is the relationship between the optimal worth control strategy and control coefficient, P and control policies, q with varying risk over time, for all other parameters remain fixed. It is observed that the investment portfolio in the risky asset is positive.

Figure 4(a, b): The effect of control coefficient, P and control policies, q on the Spatial profile of worth concentration after 365, 1000 and 3000days.

Conclusion

In this study, the Laplace transform was successfully utilized for the existence of unique solution of the heat partial differentiation equation with stochastic variables. The transform equation was expressed in terms of the volatile parameters which have effects on the system. These effects were critically examined using numerical simulations.. The aim of deriving a fractional formula for the profile of worth option payoff to analyse the deposit at each node of a tree with the insight of a binomial tree insurance model was achieved

The optimal portfolio obtained this way has less risk compared to an optimal portfolio of the classical B-S model and it becomes more negatively skewed as the expected returns of portfolios increase, which suggests that the investors trade a negative skewness for a higher expected return. A negative relation between portfolio volatility and portfolio skewness may also occur, suggesting that investors may be making a trade-off, opting for lower volatility in exchange for higher skewness, or vice versa. This trade-off indicates that stocks with significant price declines tend to exhibit increased volatility

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